

THROMBOEMBOLIC COMPLICATIONS IN PERFORATED GASTRODUODENAL ULCERS AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH THE COAGULATION AND ANTICOAGULATION SYSTEMS OF BLOOD (LITERATURE REVIEW)

J.A. Botirov¹, F.S. Tursunov², U.D. Usmonov³, A.K. Botirov⁴

Andijan State Institute, Uzbekistan^{1,2,3}

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15243157>

Abstract. *The authors report that currently, perforation of gastroduodenal ulcers is the second most common complication of peptic ulcer disease, with an incidence ranging from 2% to 32%. Postoperative complications occur in 30% of cases, and mortality after surgery ranges from 15.5% to 31%. The authors conclude that for patients in the high-risk group, the prevention of deep vein thrombosis (and, consequently, pulmonary embolism) should be considered. However, the existing drug regimens for this condition are not sufficiently effective, and the methods of preventing thromboembolic complications are often carried out without considering the state of the coagulation and anticoagulation systems of the blood, highlighting the need for further research in this area.*

Keywords: *thrombosis, gastroduodenal ulcers, mortality, surgery.*

Introduction. Perforated gastroduodenal ulcer (PGDU) is a life-threatening condition characterized by the disruption of the integrity of the corresponding organ, with its contents penetrating into the abdominal cavity [16]. Perforation is the second most common complication of peptic ulcer disease (PUD) [10] and ranges from 2% to 32% [21;33]. The localization of perforated duodenal ulcers (PDU) accounts for 70-75%, while perforated gastric ulcers (PGU) make up 25-30% [22;41]. Annually, up to 4 million people worldwide are diagnosed with peptic ulcer disease (PUD) [39]. Postoperative complications occur in 30% of cases [13]. If a patient is admitted to the hospital more than 24 hours after the onset of symptoms, the mortality rate increases to 30% [9]. The mortality rate after surgery varies from 15.5% to 31% [5;17].

The factors associated with mortality in PGDU are often late hospitalization, advanced age, comorbidities, incorrect treatment tactics, and postoperative complications [7]. For example, the mortality rate among elderly patients was more than 50 times higher compared to the average age group [25]. Venous thromboembolic complications (VTEC) is a collective term that includes deep vein thrombosis (DVT) and pulmonary artery thromboembolism (PATE) [6]. Some authors consider it appropriate to include thrombosis of the subcutaneous veins of the lower limbs (primarily in the system of the great saphenous vein) as part of VTEC. The unification of these conditions is explained by similar risk factors and a shared approach to pathogenetic therapy aimed at reducing thrombus formation.

The relevance of venous thromboembolic complications (VTEC) is determined by their high incidence and mortality, primarily associated with pulmonary artery thromboembolism (PATE). Annually, in developed countries of Europe and North America, between 39 and 115 new cases of PATE and 53-115 cases of deep vein thrombosis (DVT) are registered per 100,000 adult population. The likelihood of developing VTEC increases with age. In the elderly (≥ 80 years), the

frequency of VTEC is 8 times higher compared to younger individuals aged 50–60 years. In the structure of mortality from cardiovascular diseases in the Russian Federation, as well as globally, PATE continues to occupy one of the leading positions after myocardial infarction and stroke [15;24;26].

According to one of the largest studies, which included 6 European countries with a total population of 454.4 million people, in 2004, VTEC accounted for 370,000 deaths. Among all the deceased, the initial diagnosis of PATE was made in only 7% of cases. In 59% of cases, the diagnosis was established only during autopsy, and 34% of fatal outcomes were due to sudden death before any treatment was initiated [18;27;38].

Methodology. The process of thrombus formation in the venous system is defined by Virchow's classic triad, which includes: impaired blood circulation (blood stasis), damage to the blood vessel wall, and increased thrombus formation capability (hypercoagulation and inhibition of fibrinolysis). The key role in thrombus formation is played by the activation of blood coagulation processes, leading to fibrin formation.

VTEC (Venous Thromboembolic Complications) occur as a result of the interaction of factors predisposing to this pathology – both external, usually transient factors, and those related to the patient, which are typically difficult to eliminate. The distinction of factors based on the possibility of their elimination is important for assessing the risk of recurrence and, consequently, for deciding on the duration of anticoagulation after a VTEC episode [8;28;32].

PATE (Pulmonary Artery Thromboembolism) is a potentially life-threatening condition, with the immediate threat to life primarily related to hemodynamic disturbances caused by obstruction of the pulmonary circulation by the thrombus. The most dramatic manifestation is the development of severe hemodynamic disturbances in the form of shock. The initial hemodynamic disturbances and the associated immediate risk of fatal outcomes determine the choice of diagnostic and treatment strategies for PATE [11;15;35;42].

Ultrasound examination of the veins of the lower extremities with compression testing (CUI) is used for its diagnosis. The clinical picture of PATE (Pulmonary Artery Thromboembolism) is nonspecific, which makes its diagnosis challenging. The main signs of this condition include shortness of breath, cough, general weakness, and in some cases, chest pain and hemoptysis. Embolism with a large thrombus fragment can result in rapid fatality [2;42].

The mortality rate among untreated patients is 30-40%, while for those who begin treatment on time, it is 8-10%. The main diagnostic tool for this condition is computed tomography (CT) of the veins of the lower extremities [35;40].

Now, for all patients who have undergone PATE (Pulmonary Artery Thromboembolism), clinical evaluation of their condition is recommended 3-6 months after the acute event [2; 35]. Anticoagulant therapy is an essential component of the treatment for PATE patients [35]. Low-molecular-weight heparins have several valuable advantages (lower risk of bleeding, heparin-induced thrombocytopenia) and are preferred in the conservative treatment of PATE [24].

Results and discussion. According to the latest recommendations, an alternative to parenteral anticoagulants may be the use of new oral anticoagulants: rivaroxaban at a dose of 15 mg twice daily for the first three weeks, followed by a transition to 20 mg once daily (IB), and apixaban at a dose of 10 mg twice daily for the first week, followed by a transition to 5 mg three times daily (IB) [11;14;34].

Thrombolytic therapy is indicated for patients at high risk of early death due to PATE, with maximum effectiveness within the first 48 hours from the onset of clinical symptoms of PATE [14;35]. Thrombolytic therapy for patients with PATE is approved using streptokinase, urokinase, or tissue plasminogen activator (alteplase) [30;36].

Silina E.V. et al. (2018) emphasize the appropriateness of using direct methods for hemodynamic assessment and an individualized approach to preventive and therapeutic anticoagulation therapy [23]. Currently, surgical embolectomy is rarely used and is only indicated for patients with high-risk PATE [31;36].

The minimum duration of anticoagulant therapy after the first episode of PATE should be 3 months. This period may be extended to 6 months in the case of widespread damage to the pulmonary vascular bed. Extended use of anticoagulants reduces the risk of recurrence by nearly 90%, but the benefits of this approach are offset by an increase in major bleeding events. Therefore, at the end of the mandatory treatment course, the benefit-risk ratio of continuing anticoagulation therapy should be assessed. The lowest likelihood of venous thrombosis recurrence is associated with situations caused by initial exposure to major transient risk factors, which allows for the cessation of anticoagulation therapy 3–6 months after the first episode of PATE in this category of patients [3;29;35;37;43].

It is known that the main components of the hemostatic system are the coagulation, anticoagulation, and fibrinolytic systems. A major role in limiting the spread of coagulation is played by the tissue factor pathway inhibitor, antithrombin III, whose activity significantly increases when interacting with heparin-like glycosaminoglycans [4;12;19]. In surgical patients, the risk of VTEO depends on the trauma (extent) and duration of the surgery. The patient's somatic status at the time of surgery, the presence of comorbidities, the type of anesthesia, dehydration, and the duration of immobilization are also important factors [1;20].

Conclusion. Thus, perforated gastroduodenal ulcer is a widespread medical and social problem. In patients at risk, prevention of deep vein thrombosis (and consequently, PATE) should be considered. However, the existing drug regimens for this condition are not sufficiently effective, and the methods for preventing thromboembolic complications are carried out without considering the condition of the coagulation and anticoagulation systems, which necessitates further research.

REFERENCES

1. Abramov D.V., Zubarev A.P., Afanasyev V.M., Smolkina A.V., Karimova E.A. Perforated Duodenal Ulcer in a Patient During the Acute Period of Ischemic Stroke: A Clinical Case. *Consilium Medicum*. 2023; 25(5): 357–360.
2. Avdeev S.N., Vavilova T.V., Goncharova N.S., et al. European Guidelines for the Diagnosis and Treatment of Acute Pulmonary Artery Thromboembolism 2019: Comments from Russian Cardiological and Respiratory Societies Specialists. *Arterial Hypertension*. 2019; 25(6): 584-603.
3. Diagnosis and Treatment of Superficial Venous Thrombophlebitis in Extremities. Recommendations of the Russian Phlebologists Association, 2019 / *Phlebology*, 2019, Vol. 13, No. 2, pp. 78-97.
4. Zabolotskikh I.B., Kirov M.Yu., Afonchikov V.S., et al. Perioperative Management of Patients Receiving Long-Term Antithrombotic Therapy. *Clinical Guidelines of the Russian*

- Anesthesiologists and Resuscitators Federation. Bulletin of Intensive Care Named After A.I. Saltanov. 2019; 1: 7-19.
5. Clinical Guidelines. <https://endoexpert.ru/dokumenty-i-prikazy/klinicheskie-rekomendatsii-rokh-probodnaya-yazva-2023/>.
 6. Komarov A.L., Kropacheva E.S., Panchenko E.P. Pulmonary Artery Thromboembolism: A Textbook. Moscow, 2023. 44 p.
 7. Kosenok P.M., Vavrinchuk S.A., Boyarintsev N.I., et al. Diagnosis and Treatment of Combined Scar-Ulcerative Stenosis in Patients with Perforated Duodenal Ulcer During Organ-Sparing Operations. Far Eastern Medical Journal. 2019; No. 1, pp. 22-26.
 8. Lebedev P.A., Daushieva A.Kh., Ayupov A.M. Pulmonary Artery Thromboembolism in Clinical Practice: Risk Stratification, Diagnosis, and Treatment Algorithms. Educational Manual. Samarkand Medical University. 2015. 60 p.
 9. Lobankov V.M., Kambalov M.N., Blagonravov M.L. Incidence of Perforated Ulcers: Risk Factors. Health – The Basis of Human Potential: Problems and Solutions. 2015. No. 2.
 10. Maev I.V., Andreev D.N., Samsonov A.A., et al. Peptic Ulcer Disease: The Current State of the Problem. Medical Council. 2022. Vol. 16, No. 6, pp. 100-108.
 11. Moiseeva O.M. Pulmonary Artery Thromboembolism: Diagnosis and Treatment Algorithm. Moscow: GEOTAR-Media, 2016.
 12. Musinov I.M. Hemostasis System. Bulletin of the Russian Military Medical Academy. 2016; 3(55): 167-170.
 13. Nikitin V.N., Klipach S.G. "Difficult" Stump in Complicated Giant Penetrating Pyloroduodenal Ulcers. News of Surgery. 2017; 25(6): 574-582.
 14. Nikitin V.N., et al. Perforation of Giant Duodenal Ulcers in Elderly and Geriatric Patients. Russian Medical Journal. Medical Review. 2018; 2(2-2): 52-59.
 15. Panchenko E.P., Balakhonova T.V., Danilov N.M., et al. Diagnosis and Treatment of Pulmonary Artery Thromboembolism: Clinical Guidelines of the Eurasian Association of Cardiologists for Practicing Physicians (2021). Eurasian Cardiologic Journal. 2021; 1: 44-77.
 16. Perforated Ulcer of the Stomach and Duodenum. <https://centr-hirurgii-spb.ru/diseases/perforativnaya-yazva-zheludka-i-dvenadczatiperstnoj-kishki/>. 2025.
 17. Perforation (Penetration) of the Ulcer. <https://clinic-nail.ru/help/stati/perforatsiya-probodenie-yazvy/>. 2025.
 18. Podlipaeva A.A., Mullova I.S., Pavlova T.V., et al. New Biological Markers for Diagnosing and Predicting the Risk of Death in Patients with Pulmonary Artery Thromboembolism. Russian Cardiologic Journal. 2020; 25(4S): 4202.
 19. Podoplelova N.A., Sulimov V.B., Tashchilova A.S., et al. Blood Coagulation in the 21st Century: New Knowledge, Methods, and Prospects for Therapy. Issues of Hematology/Oncology and Immunopathology in Pediatrics. 2020; 19(1): 139-157.
 20. Russian Clinical Guidelines for the Diagnosis, Treatment, and Prevention of Venous Thromboembolic Complications. Phlebology. 2015; 9(4): 2-52.
 21. Rosstat RF. Healthcare in Russia. 2015: Statistical Yearbook of the Federal State Statistics Service. Moscow: Rosstat, 2015. 174 p.

22. Sazhin A.V., Ivakhov G.B., Stradimov E.A., et al. Surgical Treatment of Perforated Ulcers of the Stomach and Duodenum Complicated by Widespread Peritonitis: Prognosis of Outcomes (Report 2). *Endoscopic Surgery*. 2019; 25(4): 46-54.
23. Silina E.V., Rumyantseva S.A., Kabaeva E.N., Stupin V.A. Problems of Blood Coagulation System and Thromboembolic Complications in the Acute Period of Stroke. *Almanac of Clinical Medicine*. 2018; 44(3): 270-279.
24. Statkevich T.V., Pateyuk I.V., Ilyina T.V., et al. Treatment of Massive Pulmonary Artery Thromboembolism at the Present Stage. *Emergency Cardiology and Cardiovascular Risks*. 2017; 1(1): 46-51.
25. Stukachev I.N., Barsukov E.A. Urgent Treatment of Perforated Gastroduodenal Ulcers. *Scientific Journal*. 2018; 3(26).
26. Uchevatkin A.A., Yudin A.L., Kondakov A.K., et al. Differential Diagnosis of Acute and Chronic Pulmonary Artery Thromboembolism Based on MSCT Data. *Radiological Diagnosis and Therapy*. 2020; 11(4): 8-15.
27. Shatalova O.V., Smuseva O.N., Maslakov A.S., Gorbatenko V.S. Pulmonary Artery Thromboembolism: Diagnosis and Treatment. *Pharmaceutical Bulletin*. 2015; 9(4): 42-54.
28. American Society of Hematology 2020 guidelines for management of venous thromboembolism: treatment of deep vein thrombosis and pulmonary embolism. *Blood Adv* 2020 Oct 13; 4(19): 4693-4738.
29. Chaudhury P, Gadre SK, Schneider E, et al. Impact of Multidisciplinary Pulmonary Embolism Response Team Availability on Management and Outcomes. *Am J Cardiol* 2019;124(9):1465-1469.
30. Daley M.J., Pharm D.B., Sadia Ali et al. Late venous thromboembolism Profilaxir after Craniotomy in Acute Traumatic Brain injury //The American surgeon. -2015. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000313481508100236>.
31. De Gregorio M.A., Guirola J.A. et al. Interventional radiology treatment for pulmonary embolism //World J. Radiol. -2017. ((7): 295-303.; Konstantinides S.V. ESC Guidelines on the diagnosis and management of acute pulmonary embolism //Eur Heart J. -2014, vol. 53, no. 45, pp. 3145-3146.
32. Executive Summary: Antithrombotic Therapy for VTE Disease: Second Update of the CHEST Guideline and Expert Panel Report. *Chest*. 2021 Dec; 160(6): 2247-2259.
33. <https://kozlovka-crb.med.cap.ru/press/2017/9/8/169162>. -2025.
34. Kearon C., Ageno W., Cannegieter S.C. et al. Categorization of patients as having provoked or unprovoked venous thromboembolism: guidance from the SSC of ISTH //J. Thromb Haemost. -2016;14 (7):1480-1483.
35. Konstantinides S.V. Рекомендации ESC по диагностике и лечению острой легочной эмболии, разработанные в сотрудничестве с Европейским респираторным обществом (ERS), 2019 /Российский кардиологический журнал. 2020; 25(8):3848.
36. Konstantinides S.V., Meyer G., Becattini C. et al. 2019 ESC Guidelines for the diagnosis and management of acute pulmonary embolism developed in collaboration with the European Respiratory Society (ERS): The Task Force for the diagnosis and management of acute pulmonary embolism of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) //European Heart Journal. -2020;41(4):543-603.

37. Nilius H, Kaufmann J, Cuker A, Nagler M. Comparative effectiveness and safety of anticoagulants for the treatment of heparin-induced thrombocytopenia. *Am J Hematol* 2021;96(7):805-815.
38. Pyko A.A., Grigorenko E.A., Statkevich T.V. et al. Vnezapnaya serdechnaya smert': epidemiologicheskie aspekty, vozmozhnosti profilakticheskikh technologiy. *Kardiologiya v Belarusi*. -2016, № 4, S. 534-553. (in Russian).
39. Thorsen K., Søreide J.A., Kvaløy J.T. et al. Epidemiology of perforated peptic ulcer: Age and gender-adjusted analysis of incidence and mortality // *World J. Gastroenterol.* – 2013. –ol. 21, № 19. –P. 347-354.
40. Turan O., Turgut D., Gunay T., Yilmaz E., Turan A., Akkoclu A. The contribution of clinical assessments to the diagnostic algorithm of pulmonary embolism. *Adv Clin Exp Med*. -2017, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 303-309.
41. Weledji E.P. An Overview of Gastroduodenal Perforation // *Front Surg*. –2020. –Vol.7. –P. 573901.
42. Wendelboe AM, Raskob GE. Global burden of thrombosis: epidemiologic aspects. *Circ Res*. 2016; 118:1340-7.
43. Yee J, Kaide CG. Emergency Reversal of Anticoagulation. *West J Emerg Med* 2019;20(5):770-783.